
AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON WORKING FROM HOME: A POPULAR E-BUSINESS MODEL

Reshma, P. S. Aithal, Shailashree V. T. and P. Sridhar Acharya
Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore

ABSTRACT

Development in information communication and internet technologies shifts the conventional higher education and training system completely into online e-education through global universities. Students get freedom to work and simultaneously study by enrolling online in these global universities. When online education model is considered as next wave in higher education system, we propose an idea of online office model as a new system to support online education model. This paper contains the concept of "Working from Home" a online office back-up system in organizations and its advantages to customers, employees and service providers. Moreover, such model decreases the expenditure for travelling, to have better homely food etc. for the employees and the service provider can decrease expenditure for office space and maintenance. This online office management system serves as back office system present college based education system. This online office functions like conventional office system where it does all functions related to marketing, admission, enrollment, managing online study material download, online attendance, online assignment evaluation management, handling student and faculty queries, supporting examination based evaluation and finally monitoring degree/diploma certificate generation. All these online office functions can be managed and controlled by a team of online office managers working from their homes so that the physical existence of the online global education providers/universities can be totally eliminated. Working from Home system should have characteristics to fulfill its objectives to provide all the required services and to solve all problems of the stakeholders. The characteristics of "Working from Home" e-business model is analyzed using 'ABCD Analysis Technique'. Based on various factors which decides the Working from Home system, a model of various factors affecting under organizational objectives, employers point of view, employees point of view, customers/students point of view, environmental/societal point of view and system requirements are derived by a qualitative data collection instrument namely focus group method. Working from home concept is being analyzed using a new Business Analysis Frame work namely ABCD Technique.

Keywords: Working from home model, online office management, ABCD Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Working from home is defined as people working from their home or from other location of their choice other than the working area by payment which is provided by the employer. Working from home is having lots of use in recent years. Since the growth of the networking from home indicates the employee can finish their work with in their own premises. Work will be done remotely. It depends on teleworking / telecommunicating arrangements where an employee does not require staying during the business hours with their employer. In today's growing world there is an urgent need for working at home. To improve the employee retention during the busy and stress filled life we require some leisure time. Through working from home you can have free access towards a specific job through fewer interruptions from fellow employees in the office and communication time is also wider. [Baruch Y ,2001], [Bussing A,1998]

With increasing numbers of employees working at home using home as a working destination it is clear that improved employee retention, e.g. home working can help retain working parents with childcare responsibilities. [Thatcher SMB &Zhu X, 2006] It leads to increased staff motivation with less stress also. It also saves a huge expenditure towards installing a separate work office area and other facilities. A person involves in working from home can do his office work as well as home required assignments simultaneously. Allowing employees to work from home in order to encourage a better work/life balance can lead to improvements in health and well-being.

The system of working from home has some salient characteristics to fulfill its objectives and to provide all the required services, thereby solving all problems of the stake holders. "Working from Home" system should have characteristics to fulfill its objectives to provide all the required services and to solve all problems of the stake holders. The characteristics of "Working from Home" e-business model is analyzed using 'ABCD Analysis Technique'. Based on various factors which decides the Working from Home system, a model of various factors affecting under organizational objectives, employers point of view, employees point of view, customers/students point of view, environmental/societal point of view and system requirements are derived by

a qualitative data collection instrument namely focus group method. Working from home concept is being analyzed using a new Business Analysis Frame work namely ABCD Technique.

2. WORKING FROM HOME MODEL

2.1 Modeling Working-From-Home Decisions

The number of employees working from home has tripled [Mateyka, et al, 2012] Working from home has significant benefits for both the employer and the employee. According to the recent studies conducted even if the location of the study is different the results achieved in terms of the output compared to the study at office hours is rather similar. There were no changes in productivity from the working group, but those who worked from home were 13 per cent more productive. The records kept by a survey agency showed much increase in productivity earned by the employees at home and they worked more hours than that of the work done in an office. The survey revealed that the home workers also reported substantially higher work satisfaction and less work exhaustion. [Nicholas Bloom, 2013], [Cascio W F,2000][Debra et al,2005]

To anchor our thinking before examining the data we map out a simple model of the impact of working from home on: (i) firm profits, (ii) employees hours, and (iii) selection effects. Firm Profits: We model the impact on profits of WFH as primarily driven by four effects: A) Hours: The number of hours worked from the official shift (as opposed to taken on breaks) B) Call rate: The number of (quality adjusted) calls completed per hour C) Attrition: The impact on quit rates (which drive hiring and training costs) D) Capital: The impact on capital inputs, through office space and equipment requirements.

More and more people are getting to work without going to work. Instead of commuting to a corporate workspace, they're staying at home in their own space. Instead of separating their work lives from their home lives, they're blending them, or trying to. Instead of thinking of work as a place where they go, they're seeing it as something they do. While many relish the chance to strike a better work-life balance by working from home, some are surprisingly resistant to being stationed outside the office. [Harpaz, 2002]

2.2 Methods of Working from Home

The person who wish to work from home are individuals and who need additional income or a parent who wishes to earn income and stay home with kids, this is the solution for them. There are various kinds of work, which can make at home.

(1) Call centers: Selling the Time and Voice

If you have a great telephone voice, an ability to organize information quickly and a quiet place in your home to work, you could make money working for a call centre, call centre means don't have someone to answer their phones 24 hours a day. The calls are routed to a call centre. and then sent out to individuals who work from their home. These workers are equipped with computer and software are they are able to work customer's questions. [Oettinger, Gerald 2011]

(2) Selling home made products

If people are having ideas of creating beautiful things at home, this is helps them to supply the products while sitting at home. Home made products are shown no signs of stopping. E.g. Gifts, Clothes, Vegetables (farmers) etc.

(3) Consultancy

Consultants offer their services or advice for a fee. Consultants are individuals, some people use consultants for tax or financial advice, while others may pay a consultant to teach them how to set up and maintain the works. Basically if consultant is proven their skills in an area, they can market theirself as a consultant and provide services from home. [Herman Miller,2008]

Fig. 1 : Block diagram of issues affecting 'Working from Home' model.

3. ABCD ANALYSIS OF WORKING FROM HOME MODEL

Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages (ABCD) of a business model can be used to analyze and understand the model in an effective way. As per this analysis technique [P S Aithal et al 2015], the effectiveness of a business model can be studied by identifying and analysing the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages by considering various issues like organizational objectives employers and employees perspective, customer/student perspective and environmental social prospective as in the block diagram of issues affecting working from home model shown in figure 1.

The various factors contributing under the four identified constructs like advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages are derived by a qualitative data collection instrument namely focus group method [EM Rogers and S D Hunt ,1994],[R M Morgan and S D Hunt 1994] and the constituent critical elements supporting these factors are identified. Factors affecting working from home Model are (1) Factors related to organizational objectives, (2) Factors related to Employers perspective, (3) Factors related to Employees Perspective, (4) Factors related to Customers / Students service, and (5) Environmental / Social factors. Allowing staff to work at home on either a full or part-time basis can bring a range of business benefits - from increased productivity and greater staff motivation to more effective use of their premises. Home working also widens the base from which one can recruit, boosting their chances of recruiting successfully. The spread of home working is opening up a new range of possibilities for the way businesses can work and structure themselves.

As per ABCD technique we have to identify and analyse various factors and constituent critical elements under (a), (b), (c), (d), (e).

Advantages: (a) Advantages from Organizations point of view, (b) Employees Point of View, (c) Customers/Students point of view, (d) Society point of view, (e) Operational issues.

Benefits: (a) Benefits from Organizations point of view, (b) Employees Point of view, (c) Customers/Students point of view, (d) Society point of view (e) Operational issues.

Constraints: (a) Constraints from Organizations point of view, (b) Employees Point of view, (c) Customers/Students point of view, (d) Society point of view, (e) Operational issues.

Disadvantages: (a) Disadvantages from Organizations point of view, (b) Employees Point of view, (c) Customers/Students point of view, (d) Society point of view(e) Operational issues.

3.1 Organizational Issues

Freeing Work from the constraints of location and time by means of Information technology supports new patterns of work, with greater flexibility in location and time. Working in a particular location - the office - over a particular period of time - the office day - is a key feature of the way industrial work has been organized for over two centuries. This mode of working has many obvious advantages: for individuals: 'it structures their time 'it gives them social contact, 'it gives them a sense of achievement, of worth of identity. For the organization, 'it permits control and coordination of work 'it makes employees visible - hence they can be guided, evaluated, and developed 'it mandates the interaction necessary to secure consensus on organizational goals It represents a traditional, stable structure, to which the work can be accustomed. Most generally, because there is a feeling that the way they traditionally have managed. Although it can bring great benefits, working with other organisations is more complex than working alone. The success rests on a combination of formal and informal ways of achieving good working relationships on both an organisational and an individual level.

It is essential to discuss how they will work together, defining roles, responsibilities and contractual or other legal obligations, and to get this in writing in a joint working agreement. People working in collaboration also cite the importance of values, such as trust, in their relationships. However, even where they have a pre-existing relationship and trust on which to build, preparation, planning and a written agreement can help them avoid misunderstandings. It is important that staff and volunteers understand why their organisation is working collaboratively and have an insight to partners' aims and values. Time spent developing an understanding of partners' culture can help people from different organisations to work together.

3.2 Technological issues

Technology is being used in almost every company to accomplish specific tasks. Technology has changed the way people work and it has brought some fun at work, it reduces on human errors which can be caused by too much work or stress. Business technologies like computers, tablets, social networks, virtual meeting software, accounting software, customer management applications, and so much more have removed workplace boundaries and they have also facilitated in the movement of information at workplace which accelerates quick decision making at any workplace.

3.3 Environmental issues

Depending on the processes they support, wireless solutions may have to handle sub-optimal conditions such as poor lighting, rough conditions, extreme temperatures and high rates of device theft and loss. Security is an acute concern for many wireless applications. Wireless data, traveling over open airwaves, is easily intercepted. Environment conditions are addressable through a full understanding of who will use the application and how and where it will be used. Security can be enhanced using a combination of techniques, from cryptography to authentication servers, to virtual private networks. Adverse work conditions can be addressed through proper device and accessory selection, such as using ear pieces for noisy locations and backlit displays for dim lighting conditions. The advantages and the benefits are overriding the constraints and disadvantages of various environmental and social issues in case of working from home.

3.4 Employer / employee issues

Businesses perform best when there are strong working relationships between employers, employees and the business owners (e.g. shareholders). Decisions made as a result of a workforce plan inevitably both sides of the relationship – for example: A decision to make redundancies and reduce staff costs might be viewed positively by the shareholders, but negatively by the employees and trade unions. A plan to offer more flexible working options would be welcomed by employees, but might place additional pressure on the workloads of line managers. The solution to these potential conflicts and issues is usually found through communication and consultation. Ultimately, decisions need to be taken in the best interests of the business – but it is important to at least attempt to gain the support of other stakeholders.

3.5 Customer’s issues

At some point, everyone in business has to deal with an upset customer. The challenge is to handle the situation in a way that leaves the customer thinking you operate a great company. If you’re lucky, you can even encourage him or her to serve as a passionate advocate for your brand. When it comes down to it, many customers don't even bother to complain. They simply leave and buy from your competitors. Research suggests that up to 80 percent of customers who leave were, in fact, "satisfied" with the original company. Obviously, customer satisfaction is not enough. Businesses nowadays need to positively delight customers if they want to earn their loyalty. It may seem counter-intuitive, but a business owner’s ability to effectively deal with customer complaints provides a great opportunity to turn dissatisfied customers into active promoters of the business.

4. CONSTITUENT CRITICAL ELEMENTS AS PER ABCD MODEL

As per ABCD framework for Working from Home model analysis, the factors affecting under organizational, operational, technological, employer / employee, customers and social environmental issues are identified. The constituent critical elements of these factors are listed under the four constructs - advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages of the ABCD technique and tabulated in tables 1 to 4.

Table 1: Advantages of Working from home model

Sl.No.	Issue	Factors affecting	Constituent elements
1.	Organisational Issues	1. Less Investment 2. Diverse People or Workforce 3. New pattern to work 4. Organisational worth	1. High return 2. Specialized Individuals 3. Readiness to Change 4. Revenue generation
2.	Operational Issues	1. Man power Utilisation 2. Cost effective 3. Less Time consuming 4. Flexible	1. Optimum utilization of resources 2. Less cost-higher return 3. Travel time reduced 4. Flexi time
3.	Technological Issues	1. High level of technology 2. High dependency on technology 3. Expand 4. Talent	1. Preparedness of Employees 2. Quick & Instant 3. Employee empowerment
4.	Employers and employees Issues	1. Reduces staff cost 2. saving of office space 3. Balancing life & work 4. Flexible working option	1. Control mechanism 2. Increases earning 3. More productive 4. Manpower supply more

5.	Customers Issues	1. Work from anywhere 2. Faster service 3. Any time availability 4. Price	1. Enhance life 2. Competition 3. Networking 4. Affordable
6.	Social / Environmental Issues	1. Employment generation 2. Flexible working conditions 3. Stake holders satisfaction 4. Eco friendly	1. Creating opportunities 2. Clean environment 3. Employee Relationship 4. Hazards minimized

Table 2 : Benefits of Working from home model

Sl. No.	Issue	Factors affecting	Constituent elements
1.	Organisational Issues	1. Financial stability 2. More productivity 3. Attracts & Retain staff 4. Employer brand	1. Less investment in terms of office space. 2. Working at your risk 3. More supply of manpower 4. Royal Employees
2.	Operational Issues	1. Improved quality 2. Operational efficiency 3. Networking 4. Speed	1. Quality of work 2. Increases 3. Maintenance cost is less 4. Quick result
3.	Technological Issues	1. Availability 2. Technical superior 3. Improves communication 4. Ability to handle	1. Cheap & affordable 2. Latest technology 3. Formal Vs. Informal 4. Easy & safer
4.	Employers and employees Issues	1. Saves Employer Investment 2. Reduces unscheduled absence 3. Organisational structure 4. Mutuality	1. Equitable load 2. Better performance 3. Virtual 4. Interaction/ Networking
5.	Customers Issues	1. Freedom of choice 2. Matching expectation 3. Fitting to the budget	1. 24x7 service 2. Customer Vs Employees 3. Paying capacity of customers
6.	Social / Environmental Issues	1. Reduces traffic jam 2. Harmony with nature 3. Less stress 4. Improved economy	1. Pollution 2. Green habitat 3. Adaptation 4. Better living Condition

Table 3 : Constraints of Working from home model

Sl. No.	Issue	Factors affecting	Constituent elements
1.	Organisational Issues	1. Virtual organizational structure 2. Type of Business strategy 3. Leadership style	1. Role conflict 2. Not suited for manufacturing sector 3. Growth strategy 4. Democratic
2.	Operational Issues	1. Scale of production 2. Labour force 3. Suppliers 4. Finance	1. Machinery 2. Skilled 3. Just in time 4. Healthy cash flow
3.	Technological Issues	1. Full automation 2. Implementation expenses 3. Security breaches 4. Intensive training	1. Costly 2. Cost of hardware & software 3. Access to confidential data 4. Skilled labour force

4.	Employers and employees Issues	1. Makes employers lazy 2. Communication 3. Difficult to maintain skilled staff	1. Difficult to manage home & office 2. Causes distraction 3. Training 4. Motivating benefits
5.	Customers Issues	1. Reward system 2. Physical non availability 3. Customer tech savvy 4. Complicated products 5. Miscommunication	1. Employees not in work place 2. Customer training 3. Educated customer 4. Communication medium
6.	Social / Environmental Issues	1. Social media 2. Too much information 3. Occupational hazards	1. Bad reasons 2. Choice of Good Vs. Bad 3. Computers/ Phone/Laptop 4. New Diseases

Table 4 : Disadvantages of Working from home model

Sl. No.	Issue	Factors affecting	Constituent elements
1.	Organisational Issues	1. Virtual 2. Assignment 3. Disassociation 4. Organisational type 5. Organisation strategy	1. Reporting authority 2. Weak culture Sector 3. Long/Short term
2.	Operational Issues	1. Planning 2. Co-ordination becomes difficult 3. Operational control	1. Difficult 2. Tangible to intangible 3. Budget control
3.	Technological Issues	1. Disconnectedness 2. Distractions 3. Expensive 4. Crimes	1. People from people 2. Games/ Shopping etc. 3. Purchasing cost 4. Frauds
4.	Employers and employees Issues	1. Labour unions 2. Discouragement 3. Brand building 4. Absence of knowledge	1. Membership 2. More personal 3. Difficult 4. Continuous improvement of workers
5.	Customers Issues	1. Availability of Employer 2. Fun environment 3. Organisational social entity	1. Race to office 2. Lost 3. Lost
6.	Social / Environmental Issues	1. Generating e-waste 2. Face to face interaction 3. Fewer employment opportunities	1. Computers/ Mobiles 2. Lost 3. Less workforce

5. CONCLUSION

Based on ABCD analysis for the business model “working from home” various factors affecting the issues of the model along with their constituent critical elements are identified and analyst. It is found that the factors supporting advantages and benefits are more effective compare to constraints and disadvantages of this model, so that working from home model may become more popular from the prospective of employers and employees in the organization in the future.

REFERENCES

- Baruch, Y. (2001). The status of research on teleworking and an agenda for future research. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 3(2), 113-129;
- Bussing, A. (1998). Teleworking and quality of life. In P. J. Jackson & J. M. Van Der Wielen (Eds.), *Teleworking: International perspectives*. Routledge: London.
- Cascio, W. F. (2000) Managing a virtual workplace. *Academy of Management Executive*, 14 (3), 81-90;

-
-
- Harpaz, I. (2002). Advantages and disadvantages of telecommuting for the individual, organization, and society. *Work Study*, 51(2/3), 74-80
 - Mateyka, Rapino, and Landivar ,2012] Jr. Relationships between telecommuting workers and their managers: An exploratory study. *Journal of Business Communication*, 34 (4), 343-369.
 - Oettinger, Gerald, “The Incidence and Wage Consequences of Home-Based Work in the United States, 1980–2000,” *Journal of Human Resources* , 46 (2011), 237–260.
 - Thatcher, S. M. B., & Zhu, X. (2006). Changing identities in a changing workplace: Identification, identity enactment, self-verification, and telecommuting. *Academy of Management Review*, 31(4), 1075–1088.
 - Herman Miller, Inc., “Working at Home,” Herman Miller internal research report, June 2008. Peter Hall, “Out of the Shadows,” *Metropolis*, June 2008
 - World at Work, “Telework Trendlines for 2006,” World at Work/Dieringer Research Group, February, 2007.
 - Debra Moritz and Jennifer Samuells, “Gaining Buy-In for Alternative Workplace Strategies,” Jones Lang LaSalle, 2005, pp. 7.
 - P. S. Aithal, V.T. Shailashree, P. M. Suresh Kumar, A New ABCD Technique to Analyze Business Models & Concepts, *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 4, pp. 409 - 423, 2015.
 - E. M. Rogers, 'Diffusion of Innovation', 1995, The Free Press, NY.
 - R. M. Morgan, and S. D. Hunt, ‘The commitment-trust theory of relationship marketing’, *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 58, (July), pp. 20–38, 1994.